

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}^o

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Generic Top-Level Domains in the International Context

They decreased by an average of 17.34% between 2013 and 2022

The variable "Generic top-level domains (TLDs)/th pop. 15-69" refers to the number of generic top-level domains (TLDs) per 1,000 inhabitants aged 15 to 69 in a specific country or region. Generic top-level domains include extensions such as .com, .org, .net, and other non-country-specific TLDs. This metric is used to measure the penetration and use of the internet in an active population, that is, the age group most likely to use the internet for commercial, educational, social, and personal purposes. A high value of this variable indicates greater internet adoption and usage and can be an indicator of a society's digital maturity, its capacity for innovation, and its participation in the digital economy. In summary, "Generic top-level domains (TLDs)/th pop. 15-69" represents the number of generic internet domains registered per 1,000 people aged 15 to 69, providing an idea of the level of online activity and presence of a population.

Generic Top-Level Domains at the International Level in 2022. Analyzing the 2022 data for generic top-level domains (TLDs) per 1,000 inhabitants aged 15 to 69, there is a clear disparity in internet penetration and domain usage among various countries worldwide. Malta and the US top the ranking with a score of 100, indicating complete saturation of TLDs in these nations. This reflects a high level of digitalization and widespread online economic and social activities. Following are Iceland, Canada, and Luxembourg, with scores of 97.9, 86.6, and 84.8, respectively, also showing high internet adoption and a strong online presence, likely facilitated by developed economies and advanced technological infrastructures. The Netherlands and Hong Kong SAR, China, with scores of 80.9 and 75.5, respectively, are slightly below the leading group but continue to show notable TLD adoption, suggesting digitally-oriented economies with strong tech sectors. Cyprus, the UK, and Australia, with scores of 73.3, 61.6, and 61.4, respectively, reflect consistent internet penetration and high digital activity among the active population. Switzerland, Ireland, and Germany show scores of 59.6, 58.6, and 52, respectively, indicating stable economies with good digital infrastructure supporting widespread TLD usage. Denmark and Norway, with scores close to 50, continue this trend, indicating a good level of digitalization. Sweden and France, with scores of 42.8 and 42.2, respectively, also demonstrate high internet adoption, although slightly lower than the leading countries. Austria and New Zealand, with scores of 35.5 and 32.6, represent a mid-high level of TLD adoption, suggesting digitally advanced economies with room for growth compared to global leaders. Panama, Finland, and Spain, with scores of 32.1, 29.7, and 28.8, indicate robust but uneven TLD usage. Singapore,

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

with 28.3, despite being a tech hub, shows lower TLD penetration compared to its more developed Asian and European counterparts. Countries like Bulgaria, Italy, Israel, Belgium, and Slovenia, with scores ranging from 24.4 to 21.1, highlight moderate TLD adoption, reflecting economies with a good digital base but needing further investment and incentives to increase internet penetration. Portugal, the Czech Republic, and Japan, with scores between 19.6 and 16.1, show stable digital presence but with significant room for improvement. Croatia, Lithuania, Greece, and Mauritius, with scores ranging from 14.9 to 12.8, reflect emerging economies with growing internet adoption, while countries like Costa Rica, Turkey, the UAE, Estonia, and Hungary, with scores around 11, indicate good digital penetration but still far from the global leaders. Latvia, South Korea, and Namibia, with scores between 9.9 and 8.6, show economies slowly increasing their digital presence. Countries like Kuwait, Poland, North Macedonia, Brunei Darussalam, and Malaysia, with scores ranging from 7.7 to 6.8, indicate more limited TLD adoption, suggesting the need for targeted policies to boost internet usage. Albania, Uruguay, and Thailand, with scores between 6.7 and 5.5, show growing digital usage but still below potential. Countries like Peru, Jordan, Romania, Ukraine, Bahrain, and Trinidad and Tobago, with scores between 5.1 and 4.3, reflect economies where TLD adoption is moderate but expanding. Latin American nations like Guatemala, Argentina, and Colombia, with scores between 3.8 and 2.9, show low TLD penetration, reflecting economic and infrastructural challenges limiting internet adoption. Countries like South Africa, Mexico, Nicaragua, Saudi Arabia, and Tunisia, with scores around 2.7, indicate limited digital presence that could benefit from significant investments in digital infrastructure. China, with a score of 2.5, surprises with low generic TLD penetration despite its huge population and growing digital economy, suggesting a strong use of country-specific TLDs like .cn. Other countries like the Dominican Republic, El Salvador, Vietnam, and Chile, with similar scores, show similar challenges in adopting generic TLDs. Ecuador, Moldova, Jamaica, Laos, Georgia, Iran, Belarus, Montenegro, and Brazil, with scores between 2 and 1.6, indicate economies with limited digital presence. Countries like Morocco, Oman, Paraguay, Indonesia, and Serbia, with scores ranging from 1.6 to 1.5, reflect low TLD penetration, suggesting the need to improve internet infrastructure and incentivize digital adoption. The Philippines, Egypt, Cambodia, and Botswana, with scores around 1, indicate very limited TLD penetration, which could be improved with targeted government policies and investments in technology infrastructure. The lowest-ranked countries, like Senegal, Azerbaijan, India, Kenya, and Nigeria, with scores around 0.9, reflect significant challenges in TLD adoption, suggesting the need for structural reforms and investments to improve internet access. Countries like Sri Lanka, Benin, Ghana, Honduras, Mongolia, Pakistan, and Togo, with scores around 0.6, show very limited digital presence. Algeria, Nepal, Zimbabwe, Bangladesh, and Côte d'Ivoire, with scores of 0.5, indicate severe infrastructural deficiencies hindering TLD adoption. Nations like Kazakhstan, Yemen, Cameroon, Iraq, Kyrgyzstan, Uganda, Burundi, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Madagascar, Mali, Myanmar, Mauritania, Rwanda, Tajikistan, and Tanzania, with scores between 0.3 and 0.1, reflect practically non-existent TLD penetration, suggesting severe economic and infrastructural challenges impeding digital growth. Finally, Angola, Ethiopia, Mozambique, and Uzbekistan, with a score of 0, have virtually no TLD presence, indicating a critical lack of digital infrastructure and internet access.

Generic Top-Level Domains at the International Level between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing the data for generic top-level domains (TLDs) from 2013 to 2022 reveals notable variations, both positive and negative, among countries, indicating significant changes in internet adoption and online presence. In terms of growth, Cambodia and Senegal show the most impressive rates, with increases of 266.67% and 233.33%, respectively. This rapid growth suggests that both countries are making significant

progress in expanding internet access and encouraging domain registration, likely through favorable government policies and investments in digital infrastructure. Albania saw an increase of 204.55%, rising from 2.2 to 6.7 TLDs per 1,000 inhabitants, reflecting significant improvements in internet access and usage, possibly due to structural reforms and the expansion of telecommunications networks. Togo and Mongolia also recorded significant growths of 200% and 100%, respectively, although starting from a very low base. These increases indicate targeted efforts to improve connectivity and promote digitalization in countries with historically limited infrastructure. Malta, already in a strong position in 2013 with 53.3 TLDs, doubled its online presence, reaching a score of 100 in 2022, an 87.62% increase. This growth can be attributed to a strong push towards digitalization, supported by a service-oriented economy and a favorable regulatory environment. Other countries like Brunei Darussalam, Armenia, and Moldova showed significant growth, with increases of 106.06%, 82.35%, and 81.82%, respectively, suggesting effective policies in promoting internet use and domain registration. Despite these positive growths, many countries recorded decreases in their TLDs. South Korea and Japan, for example, saw decreases of 21.62% and 20.69%, respectively. This decline could indicate a saturated market or shifts in user preferences towards other forms of online presence, such as social media. Germany and the UK, with decreases of 26.35% and 26.58%, perhaps reflect market consolidation or a migration towards country-specific domains (ccTLDs). Countries like France and Switzerland recorded decreases of 19.92% and 32.88%, respectively. This could suggest a market dynamic shift, where businesses and individuals prefer more specific domains or new domain extensions that better represent their digital identity. In Ireland and Australia, where decreases were 31.06% and 32.97%, respectively, a similar trend is observed, perhaps attributable to an increase in available options for online presence and growing competition among different TLDs. Some countries showed extremely pronounced declines. For example, Namibia and Kazakhstan saw reductions of 71.43% and 62.50%, respectively. These figures indicate significant structural problems or ineffective policies in supporting TLD adoption. Azerbaijan and Sri Lanka, with decreases of 76.32% and 68%, suggest severe difficulties in maintaining a stable level of domain registrations. Egypt and Jordan recorded decreases of 36.84% and 37.66%, respectively, indicating that despite initial growth, there have been significant setbacks, possibly due to political instability or changes in economic policies. Countries like Israel and Turkey also saw substantial decreases of 28.99% and 29.38%, respectively, indicating that despite a well-developed digital infrastructure, there have been changes negatively affecting the number of TLD registrations. Another interesting trend emerges from data of countries with advanced economies. For example, Canada and Luxembourg, which had very high TLD registration rates in 2013, saw significant decreases in 2022, of 13.4% and 15.2%, respectively. This might reflect a saturated market or a shift towards more flexible and modern forms of digital presence.

Internet Governance and the Increase in Top-Level Domains. The increase in generic top-level domains (TLDs) can be considered positive in several respects, though it presents some challenges. On one hand, the growth of TLDs reflects greater internet penetration and usage, which is essential for economic development, innovation, and global connectivity. A growing number of TLDs indicates that more people, businesses, and organizations are establishing an online presence, which can facilitate e-commerce, access to information, and communication. This is particularly important in an era where the digital economy is rapidly expanding, and internet access has become fundamental for economic and social participation. The increase in TLDs can also stimulate competition and innovation in the technology sector. With more domains available, businesses have more opportunities to choose domain names that best represent their brand and services, thus enhancing

their online visibility. This can lead to a more dynamic market where new businesses can compete more effectively with established entities. Additionally, an increase in TLDs can incentivize internet service providers to improve their infrastructure and offer more efficient and competitive domain registration services. However, the increase in TLDs also presents some challenges. Greater domain availability can lead to increased complexity in managing and monitoring domain names. With more options available, businesses and individuals may find it difficult to choose the most appropriate domain and protect their online identity. Additionally, the proliferation of TLDs can increase the risk of cybersquatting, where third parties register domains with the intent to sell at high prices or profit from the use of well-known brands. Another negative aspect could be the fragmentation of the digital ecosystem. With an increasing number of TLDs, users may find it challenging to navigate and find reliable information online. This could lead to reduced trust in search tools and digital platforms. Furthermore, an increase in TLDs without a corresponding growth in digital skills and awareness among users might limit the potential benefits of network expansion. Finally, the increase in TLDs can have implications for internet governance. Managing and regulating TLDs requires international collaboration and effective oversight to ensure the system remains secure, stable, and accessible. This implies that policies and practices related to TLD management must be transparent and inclusive, involving a wide range of stakeholders from governments to private organizations and civil society.

Conclusions. Generic top-level domains per 1,000 inhabitants decreased on average in the countries considered between 2013 and 2022 by 17.34%, from 18.74 units to 15.47 units. However, there are countries where this value increased significantly above the period average, such as Cambodia with a value of 266.67%, Senegal with +233.33%, Albania with +204.55%, Togo with +200.00%, and Botswana with +150.00%. There are also countries where the reduction in the number of generic top-level domains was much more severe than the average, such as Namibia with -71.43%, Kyrgyz Republic, Tanzania, and Zambia with -75.00%, and Azerbaijan with -76.32%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+63>

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4782193.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771132.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe. Available at SSRN 4103840.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The opportunity driven entrepreneurship in the context of innovation systems in Europe in the period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The impact of patent applications on technological innovation in European countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-22.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3), 1-13.

